

EFFECTS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEM STANDARDIZATION ON FIRMS: EVIDENCE FROM TEXT MINING ANNUAL REPORTS.

ABSTRACT

Using a management formula to standardize innovation management can be thought of as deeply contradictory, ~~but~~ however, several ~~successful~~ successful firms in Spain have been certified under the pioneer innovation management standard UNE 166002. This paper analyzes the effects that standardization has in the attitudes and values ~~about~~ as regard to innovation ~~effor~~ a sample of firms by text-mining their corporate disclosures. Changes in the relevance of the concepts, co-word networks and emotion analysis have been employed to conclude that the effects of certification on the corporate behavior about innovation are coincident with the open innovation and transversalization concepts that ~~the~~ UNE 166002 ~~motivates~~ promotes.

INTRODUCTION

The very concept of standardizing innovation management may sound bizarre and counterintuitive to the reader: spontaneity, ~~freshness~~ originality and flexibility are some of the main features usually attributed to innovation, ~~while~~ whereas increased bureaucracy, adherence to rules and repetitiveness are often related to management standards. While a substantial amount of research is devoted to ~~analyze~~ analyzing the effects of management standards on ~~a~~ firm's performance, their effects on ~~the~~ innovative capacity remain largely under-researched. This paper aims ~~at analyzing~~ to analyze the influence of certification under the pioneer innovation management standard UNE 166002 on the innovation efforts being conducted by ~~the~~ firms, exploiting the textual information contained in annual reports of ~~firms~~ companies certified under ~~such~~ the said standard.

UNE 166002, a pioneer standard in innovation management

The first experimental version of ~~the~~ innovation management standard UNE 166002 was released in 2002, based on the recommendations stated in Oslo, Frascati and Bogota manuals, and ~~it~~ this is considered to be a pioneer standard in the field of ~~innovation management~~ of innovation. Innovation management guidelines do exist in the market, such as ~~the~~ BS 7000 in the UK ~~but, nevertheless~~, as far as the authors are concerned, this is the first fully operative innovation management standard backed by a national standardization agency (AENOR) and a recognized body of auditors. In the debate about the effects of management standards ~~in firm's~~ on company innovation, ~~the~~ UNE 166002 becomes the elephant in the room, bringing together two issues deemed ~~by the mainstream~~ to be deeply divergent ~~by the mainstream:~~ ~~the~~; bureaucratic ~~stiffness~~ inflexibility of standards and the ~~sparky~~ dynamic, spontaneous nature of

innovation. A ~~revision~~review of the literature ~~brings evidences supporting~~provides evidence to support that ~~well-known~~recognized management standards such as ISO 9001 can indeed improve innovation by aligning a firm's resources towards better customer orientation, employee involvement and improved leadership (Pekovic & Galia, 2009) and at the same time deepening the managerial understanding of ~~managers about how~~ the nuts and bolts of the ~~firm~~firm's work by means of systematic codification and recording of activities (Anderson, 1999). ~~The~~ Customer-focused management principles that form the basis of many management standards can also help to connect functional areas and overcome the rigidities of formal structure, thus facilitating process innovations (Terziovski & Guerrero, 2014) while other studies assert that both product and process innovations benefit from the implementation of quality management standards (Kim, Kumar, & Kumar, 2012; Prajogo & Hong, 2008). As a counterpart, management standards condition individuals to a set of predetermined data, tools and techniques that could lead to lower~~reduced~~ flexibility, less ~~openness~~willingness to change and adherence to repeated behavior (Pekovic & Galia, 2009; Prajogo & Sohal, 2004). In addition to this, the routinization of problem solving (Glynn, 1996) and the focus on documentation, standardization and conformity to rules and procedures may damage the culture of innovation (Naveh & Erez, 2004). The academic debate about this issue is far from achieving a consensus.

~~Evidences until this~~Evidence to date regarding the influence of UNE 166002 on firms ~~point out~~indicates that its implementation may lead to an enhanced use of information ~~in~~within the firm, via the systematization of information retrieval and spread phases in competitive intelligence (Pineda, 2015), particularly when proper IT support is available to avoid infoxication ~~problems~~issues (Mir-Mauri & Fa, 2008). ~~Unavoidably~~Inevitably, researchers will have to deal with significant extra workload from the maintenance of documentation and information systems and a rooted innovation culture is necessary to avoid a lack of motivation or even outright opposition to the whole system (Mir-Mauri & Casadesús, 2011). ~~Staff's~~Staff perception of UNE 166002 advantages is improved when knowledge management at the firm gets~~is~~ reinforced by the increased amount and homogeneity of information available. Stage-gate procedures for R&D project management also gain objectivity and favor a data-driven mindset ~~on~~in innovation managers when the standard's requirements are adequately implemented, as some case studies show (Garechana, Río-Belver, Cilleruelo-Carrasco, & Bidosola, n.d.).

Text mining of corporate disclosures

The possibilities of complementing quantitative financial information with the automated analysis of textual information contained in corporate disclosures has attracted the attention of the scientific community since the work~~work~~ of Back et al. (2001), among

others. The quantitative information of a corporate report deals with the past (Butler & Kešelj, 2009), ~~while~~~~whereas~~ the qualitative part ~~holds some message~~~~contains information~~ about future company performance and managerial expectations that ~~can~~~~might~~ be helpful to reveal insiders' moods and ~~anticipation~~~~expectations~~ about the future performance of their company (Kloptchenko et al., 2004).

There is a significant corpus of research dealing with the processing of textual information to predict bankruptcy, fraud (Cecchini, Aytug, Koehler, & Pathak, 2010; Goel & Gangolly, 2012; Shirata, Takeuchi, Ogino, & Watanabe, 2011) or financial performance (Balakrishnan, Qiu, & Srinivasan, 2010; Li, 2006; Qiu, Srinivasan, & Hu, 2014), but the study of changes in corporate attitude or governance by means of text mining has ~~somehow~~ received ~~somehow~~—less attention. ~~However~~~~Nonetheless~~, the rise of environmental concerns and the increasing amount of firms that publish Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) reports has led to the publication of interesting research about the interaction of firms with both their social and natural environment (Liew, Adhitya, & Srinivasan, 2014; Saha & Nabareseh, 2015) or ~~the~~ particular characteristics of ~~the~~ CSR information being disclosed (Liu ZhenYa & Jiang Yan, 2014; Modapothala & Issac, 2009). As far as the authors are concerned, this study ~~has no precedent~~~~is unprecedented~~ in analyzing changes in ~~company's~~~~company~~ values and attitudes towards innovation by text-mining ~~the~~ annual reports, ~~but~~~~however~~, there are interesting precedents in ~~the~~ literature based ~~in~~~~on~~ web scraping techniques to develop a taxonomy of innovation (Libaers, Hicks, & Porter, 2016) or validating website data for innovation studies (Gök, Waterworth, & Shapira, 2015).

Corporate reports are extensive, free-text documents that ~~serve~~~~are used~~ for multiple purposes both ~~in~~~~inside~~ and ~~out~~~~outside~~ the firm, and several aspects have to be taken into account when text-mining such a data source. Kenneth (2011) found that R&D related disclosures present in 10-K reports are lower when earnings perform positively, showing that the firm's financial performance exerts some influence ~~in~~~~over~~ the type of information ~~the~~~~that~~ firms choose to emphasize in their disclosures. Some ~~work~~~~papers are~~ also ~~set a~~~~warning~~~~cautionary~~ about text-mining textual items such as corporate reports: standard dictionaries often perform poorly when analyzing financial information, and ~~a~~ specific emotion analysis lexicon should be employed when analyzing financial texts (Loughran & McDonald, 2011). Li (2010) also expresses concerns about the authorship of corporate disclosures, much of ~~them~~ ~~being~~~~which are~~ collectively authored by managers, auditors, lawyers and public relations staff, thus being prone to ~~have~~~~contain~~ biased information.

METHOD

This study will analyze the concepts present in the annual reports of firms certified under innovation management standard UNE 166002 using text mining tools, ~~trying attempting~~ to characterize managerial changes in innovation that took place after ~~standardizing having~~ standardized their innovation management systems ~~according to in accordance with~~ the guidelines established by UNE 166002.

Data

The starting point of this study is a sample provided by the Spanish Association for Normalization and Certification (AENOR) consisting of 243 firms certified under UNE 166002 since year 2002. ~~The~~ Public availability of annual reports was checked for each firm by looking at their websites on the Internet, ~~finding revealing~~ that many firms had ~~been closed down ceased trading~~ while others had been absorbed or merged, thus ~~losing losing~~ their independent identity. From the remaining firms just twelve ~~had made~~ enough annual reports available; ~~;~~ both before and after the year of certification ~~year;~~ to conduct the study. The reporting habit had substantially changed ~~across throughout~~ the years for ~~some certain~~ firms, the most frequent modification being the inclusion of a CSR chapter or separate CSR report in ~~the~~ latter years, but also the splitting of annual reports ~~in into~~ separate chapters such as “governance ~~memories accounts~~” “economic ~~memories accounts~~” and so on.

Given the reduced size (12) of the final ~~firm~~ sample of firms, the authors were able to check the available files one by one and ~~only the those~~ reports containing pure financial information such as P&L or balance sheets were discarded in this study. CSR reports were included in the analysis since they were often ~~had direct connection~~ directly connected with innovation projects of the firm, particularly those related with good environmental practices and the sustainability of products and processes. The final dataset consisted of 136 files containing the reports of twelve firms.

Text mining using Vantage Point®

The textual information contained in the reports was ~~transformed to xml format~~ transposed from the original pdf files to xml format and imported into Vantage Point® (VP) software, generating separate datasets for the reports dated before and after the certification year. Data ~~was were~~ processed using VP’s Natural Language Processing (NLP) function in order to extract the word frequencies and the words “Innovation” and “Research” (including their declensions) were selected as Significant for Innovation (SI) terms from which to extract the main concepts related with innovation from the text.

This step was conducted using the “Extract nearby phrases” command in VP to explore the main concepts present in the vicinity of SI terms that could be further analyzed ~~looking~~

~~for~~ by identifying text patterns and emotions associated with innovation. The limit of such vicinity was set into just one sentence in order to avoid noise as much as possible. The selection of such a reduced number of terms deemed to be SI had the same objective, since increasing the breadth of ~~the scope~~ quickly escalated rapidly increased the amount of noise introduced in the analysis. Once the concepts in the vicinity of SI terms were extracted, all punctuation, corrupted terms and numbers were removed and VP's "list cleanup" command was run using "Organization Name" fuzzy matching file in order to merge declensions and similar compound terms. The text mining process produced a field containing innovation-related terms as extracted from the corporate reports and ordered by frequency, both for pre-certification and post-certification datasets. Additionally, a co-occurrence matrix of the 100 most frequently occurring terms was built in VP and their cosine similarity was calculated to generate network visualizations of the relationships between innovation-related concepts.

Proportion, emotion analysis and mapping

The comparison of the relative frequencies of innovation-related terms was made by subsetting the terms that were present both in pre and post-certification datasets and plotting their relative frequencies as shown in figure 1 in ~~section~~ the "Results"- section. This analysis allows the identification of concepts that change their relative weight in reports after ~~the~~ certification, pointing out revealing changes in corporate attitude towards innovation. This has been complemented by emotion analysis of the innovation-related terms, conducted by using NRC word-emotion association lexicon (EmoLex) (Mohammad & Turney, 2013) available in R package tidytext¹. Finally, term co-occurrence networks were built using VosViewer software in order to visualize changes between concept relationships as a consequence of certification under UNE 166002.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The comparison between the occurrence frequencies of concepts both present in pre and post-certification datasets ~~can~~ could help us explore the changes in corporate attitude towards innovation. Terms located away from the diagonal in figure 1 experiment experience the biggest proportional change:

¹ <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=tidytext>

shows the top 10 managerial concepts that experimentexperience the biggest change after certification:

Term	% change in proportion
startup	9.89
constant evolution	9.89
second generation	9.89
Seventh Framework Program	9.05
outsourcing	6.54
environmental setting	6.54
total budget	6.12
RDi activities	5.7
inception	5.7
leading global company	5.7

Table 1. Top 10 managerial concepts, according to theas per % of change.

The significant emergence of terms such as “startup” and “outsourcing” point to an increased reliance on external sources for innovation. The growth of presence of FP7 is also indicative of an orientation of firms towards external funding sources for their research, and environmental issues show an increasing connection with innovation. The main concepts that loselose relevance correspond to geographical locations and technologies that have been replaced acrossover time.

The emotion analysis conducted in this study is based on Plutchik’s wheel of emotions model, where similar emotions are placed next to each other and contrasting emotions diametrically opposite to each other. The proximity to the center reflects an increased intensity of the emotions (Mohammad & Turney, 2013).

Figure 2. Depiction of Plutchik's wheel of emotions (Source: Wikimedia Commons).

Results presented in figure 3 show that "Trust" is the predominant emotion linked to innovation, followed by "Anticipation". The former reflects positive features based on reliance on a valuable resource, while the latter recalls shows words linked to future events. Finally "Joy", closely linked to words evoking satisfaction, is the third main emotion present in the dataset. The predominance of these feelings is coherent with the

mainstream values associated with innovations. Both “Trust” and “Joy” grow in importance after certification while “Anticipation” decreases in its share-proportion.

Figure 3. Main emotions present in the dataset, before and after ~~the~~ certification under UNE 166002.

“Fear” and “Sadness” are the main negative emotions associated with innovation. This was a surprising finding that was only better understood by delving a bit slightly deeper

into data: One of the firms present in the sample is a university hospital, and the emotion dictionary in EmoLex associates disease names, as well as many bodily function names, to such unpleasant emotions. Other negative emotions are present into a lesser extent and looselose their relevance after certification.

Finally, variations in the relationships between innovation-related concepts were analyzed exporting term co-occurrence matrices to VosViewer clustering and visualization software, results are shown in **figures 4 and 5**:

Figure 5. Word co-occurrence networks for post-certification data. Top 100 words are shown, according to their frequency.

The pre-certification map shows a loosely connected group of terms difficult to interpret (blue-yellow) and two separated clusters that point at a separation between the managerial (red) and the scientific (green) aspects of innovation. On the other sidehand, the post-certification map shows a more neat neater structure where R&D (red) is apart+distant from innovation (green), the latter being strongly connected to CSR issues. A third cluster (blue) shows technostructural/techno-structural terms that could be associated to with an increased specialization and professionalization in innovation management.

CONCLUSIONS

This work studies the influence that the certification under innovation management standard UNE 166002 has in-the on corporate perceptions and values regarding innovation. With this purpose in mind, a sample of twelve firms certified under UNE 166002 has been selected based on the availability of a sufficient number of corporate reports both before and after the certification year. These reports have been text-mined using the NLP tools provided by Vantage Point® software to capture the concepts occurring in the vicinity of SI terms and the changes in concepts and their relationships, in addition to the emotions, have been analyzed.

First of all, ~~evidences have~~evidence has been found that the ~~precision~~accuracy of the method followed is satisfactory. The analysis of relative ~~word proportions~~word proportions pre and post certification shows the increasing relevance of emergent technologies in the firm's innovative effort and the decay of older technologies, ~~just as should~~would be expected if this approach were to successfully capture the firm's behavior ~~about~~regarding innovation. Proportion analysis also shows the emergence of terms that ~~point at~~indicate a more open, more collaborative concept of innovation. This is coincident with the philosophy of open innovation embedded in the UNE 166002 standard (AENOR, 2016)

The analysis of the co-occurrence network shows that a pre-certification cluster formed by science-research-~~universities~~university related terms disappears after ~~the~~ certification, the "scientific" terms now being spread across three different clusters. This could be ~~pointing at~~illustrating a less isolated concept of research and science after ~~the~~ certification. Other phenomena observed are the emergence of a cluster that we describe as "technocratic", after ~~the~~ certification. This could be signaling the introduction of management practices in innovation similar to those established by ~~the widespread~~prevalent quality management standards. Finally, a remarkable post-certification link is established ~~post-certification~~ between concepts pertaining to the field of CSR and innovation, ~~this~~which seems reasonable given the increasing importance of resource-efficiency and sustainability in many technological fields and the overall positive perception of innovative firms in society, the green-and-innovative firm brand being something that many firms are willing to include in their CSR reports.

Emotion analysis revealed that "trust" is the prevailing emotion associated with innovation, and that its importance clearly grows after certification. This is indicative of a stronger commitment with innovation and an increased faith in its play~~role~~ for the successful future of the company. The importance of ~~emotion~~the "anticipation" emotion shows ~~planificati~~ona firm's planning and attentiveness ~~of firms regarding~~with regard to innovation. The presence of negative emotions associated with innovation is explained by the presence of a university hospital in the ~~firm~~sample of firms: disease and medical words have negative connotations in our emotion analysis model.

We can conclude that the influence of the UNE 166002 standard in the concepts and attitudes that the certified firms ~~show about~~present in relation to innovation seems to be well aligned with the purposes of the standard: The implementation of open innovation concepts in the management of innovation and the migration from an isolated, departmentalized R&D concept to a transversal concept of innovation, are embedded in several activities of the firm. The implementation of UNE 166002 ~~can~~may also explain the overall increase in positive emotions towards innovation. This being said, this study presents some shortcomings that, being akin to those present in many other text mining

studies, ~~must however~~should be explained here. First, the evolution in concepts and vocabulary present in the annual reports is affected by many variables apart from the certification under UNE 166002: Annual reports ~~use to be~~become more complete and professionally written over time, thus changing ~~it~~their vocabulary and structure. The popularity of the green economy can also exert great influence ~~in the on~~ company disclosures ~~of the company~~, with ~~the~~—CSR reports playing a brand-building (~~propagandistic?~~)self-publicizing role that can distort the analysis. Attitude and value changes such as those we are trying to unveil in this analysis ~~use to be~~are usually gradual, and dramatic changes are easier to detect in the written language used by the managers of the company (Kloptchenko et al., 2004). In spite of these shortcomings, we think that this ~~piece of~~research ~~can~~work may add useful ~~insight about~~insights into the behavior of firms and the nature of innovation, particularly considering the very controversial nature of innovation management standards and the unresolved debate ~~about on~~ the influence of standardization in the innovation capacity of ~~the~~ firms.

REFERENCES

- AENOR. (2016). UNE 166002 R&D&I Management Systems. Retrieved from http://www.en.aenor.es/aenor/certificacion/innovacion/innovacion_sistemas_166002.asp#.Vy5DAoThDak
- Anderson, S. (1999). Why firms seek ISO 9000 certification: regulatory compliance or competitive advantage? *Production and Operations Management*, 8(1), 28–43. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/openview/90cdaedc8b7b40cc75a199420e7b6fb0/1?pq-origsite=gscholar>
- Back, B., Toivonen, J., Vanharanta, H., & Visa, A. (2001). Comparing numerical data and text information from annual reports using self-organizing maps. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, 2(4), 249–269. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S1467-0895\(01\)00018-5](http://doi.org/10.1016/S1467-0895(01)00018-5)
- Balakrishnan, R., Qiu, X. Y., & Srinivasan, P. (2010). On the predictive ability of narrative disclosures in annual reports. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 202(3), 789–801. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2009.06.023>
- Butler, M., & Kešelj, V. (2009). Financial Forecasting Using Character N-Gram Analysis and Readability Scores of Annual Reports (pp. 39–51). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-01818-3_7
- Cecchini, M., Aytug, H., Koehler, G. J., & Pathak, P. (2010). Making words work: Using financial text as a predictor of financial events. *Decision Support Systems*, 50(1), 164–175. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2010.07.012>

- Garechana, G., Río-Belver, R., Cilleruelo-Carrasco, E., & Bildosola, I. (n.d.). INNOVATION MANAGEMENT AT ABENGOA SOLAR NEW TECHNOLOGIES: IMPACT OF STANDARD UNE 166002 AND PATENT STRATEGY. *Creativity and Innovation Management*.
- Glynn, M. A. (1996). Innovative genius: a framework for relating individual and organizational intelligences to innovation. *Academy of Management Review*, 21(4), 1081–1111. <http://doi.org/10.5465/AMR.1996.9704071864>
- Goel, S., & Gangolly, J. (2012). BEYOND THE NUMBERS: MINING THE ANNUAL REPORTS FOR HIDDEN CUES INDICATIVE OF FINANCIAL STATEMENT FRAUD. *Intelligent Systems in Accounting, Finance and Management*, 19(2), 75–89. <http://doi.org/10.1002/isaf.1326>
- Gök, A., Waterworth, A., & Shapira, P. (2015). Use of web mining in studying innovation. *Scientometrics*, 102(1), 653–671. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-014-1434-0>
- Kenneth, J. M. (2011). *More than Numbers: R&D-related Disclosure and Firm Performance*. University of Michigan.
- Kim, D.-Y., Kumar, V., & Kumar, U. (2012). Relationship between quality management practices and innovation. *Journal of Operations Management*, 30(4), 295–315. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2012.02.003>
- Kloptchenko, A., Eklund, T., Karlsson, J., Back, B., Vanharanta, H., & Visa, A. (2004). Combining data and text mining techniques for analysing financial reports. *Intelligent Systems in Accounting, Finance & Management*, 12(1), 29–41. <http://doi.org/10.1002/isaf.239>
- Li, F. (2006). Do Stock Market Investors Understand the Risk Sentiment of Corporate Annual Reports? *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.898181>
- Li, F. (2010). Textual Analysis of Corporate Disclosures: A Survey of the Literature. *Journal of Accounting Literature*, 29, 143–165.
- Libaers, D., Hicks, D., & Porter, A. L. (2016). A taxonomy of small firm technology commercialization. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 25(3), 371–405. <http://doi.org/10.1093/icc/dtq039>
- Liew, W. Te, Adhitya, A., & Srinivasan, R. (2014). Sustainability trends in the process industries: A text mining-based analysis. *Computers in Industry*, 65(3), 393–400. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2014.01.004>
- Liu ZhenYa, & Jiang Yan. (2014). Analysis of Multi-dimensional Characteristics of Corporate Social Responsibility Report—Using China's Listed Companies in 2011 as the Case Study. *Journal of Nanjing University of Finance and Economics*. Retrieved from http://en.cnki.com.cn/Article_en/CJFDTotl-NJJJ201405010.htm
- Loughran, T., & McDonald, B. (2011). When Is a Liability Not a Liability? Textual Analysis,

- Dictionaries, and 10-Ks. *The Journal of Finance*, 66(1), 35–65.
<http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.2010.01625.x>
- Mir-Mauri, M., & Casadesús, M. (2011). Standardised innovation management systems: A case study of the Spanish Standard UNE 166002:2006. *Innovar*, 21(40), 171–188. Retrieved from http://www.scielo.org.co/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0121-50512011000200013&lng=en&nrm=iso&tlng=en
- Mir-Mauri, M., & Fa, M. (2008). Une 166002: 2006: estandarizar y sistematizar la i+ d+ i la norma y la importancia de las tic en su implementación. *DYNA-Ingeniería E Industria*, 83(6), 325–331. Retrieved from <http://www.revistadyna.com/Documentos/pdfs%255C200806sep%255C1479DYNAINDEX.pdf>
- Modapothala, J. R., & Issac, B. (2009). Study of economic, environmental and social factors in sustainability reports using text mining and Bayesian analysis. In *2009 IEEE Symposium on Industrial Electronics & Applications* (pp. 209–214). IEEE.
<http://doi.org/10.1109/ISIEA.2009.5356467>
- Mohammad, S., & Turney, P. (2013). Crowdsourcing a Word–Emotion Association Lexicon. *Computational Intelligence*, 29(3), 436–465.
- Naveh, E., & Erez, M. (2004). Innovation and Attention to Detail in the Quality Improvement Paradigm. *Management Science*, 50(11), 1576–1586. Retrieved from <http://pubsonline.informs.org/doi/abs/10.1287/mnsc.1040.0272>
- Pekovic, S., & Galia, F. (2009). From quality to innovation: Evidence from two French Employer Surveys. *Technovation*, 29(12), 829–842.
<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2009.08.002>
- Pineda, Á. (2015). Sistematizar con éxito la innovación: UNE 166002 Integrated Circuits Málaga. *AENOR: Revista de la normalización y la certificación*. AENOR, Asociación Española de Normalización y Certificación. Retrieved from <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=5278810&info=resumen&idioma=SPA>
- Prajogo, D. I., & Hong, S. W. (2008). The effect of TQM on performance in R&D environments: A perspective from South Korean firms. *Technovation*, 28(12), 855–863. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2008.06.001>
- Prajogo, D. I., & Sohal, A. S. (2004). The multidimensionality of TQM practices in determining quality and innovation performance — an empirical examination. *Technovation*, 24(6), 443–453. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4972\(02\)00122-0](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4972(02)00122-0)
- Qiu, X. Y., Srinivasan, P., & Hu, Y. (2014). Supervised learning models to predict firm performance with annual reports: An empirical study. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65(2), 400–413.
<http://doi.org/10.1002/asi.22983>

- Saha, A., & Nabareseh, S. (2015). Communicating Corporate Social Responsibilities: Using Text Mining for a Comparative Analysis of Banks in India and Ghana. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(3), 11–20. <http://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2015.v6n3s1p11>
- Shirata, C. Y., Takeuchi, H., Ogino, S., & Watanabe, H. (2011). Extracting Key Phrases as Predictors of Corporate Bankruptcy: Empirical Analysis of Annual Reports by Text Mining. *Journal of Emerging Technologies in Accounting*, 8(1), 31–44. <http://doi.org/10.2308/jeta-10182>
- Terziovski, M., & Guerrero, J.-L. (2014). ISO 9000 quality system certification and its impact on product and process innovation performance. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 158, 197–207. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2014.08.011>